

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: UDEMEZUE****FIRST NAME: INNOCENT****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references.

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Chicago Manual of Style Cribb Sheet (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)
4. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
5. Latin Abbreviations & Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)

IMPROVING ACAMEDIC WRITING SKILLS

1) SUMMARY

This response paper is a review of one of the seven study periods of ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack designed to empower new graduate students at Euclid university with a clear understanding of the fundamentals of international academic writing (EUCLID 2020, 2). The second edition of Cleenewerck and Gulma's ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack for period one examines concisely and expansively, and within eight chapters, the prerequisite techniques, and guidelines necessary for creating concise, informative, and compelling essays that boost student's academic performance.

Emphatically, the first chapter discusses the basics of essay writing including the nature, structure, basic steps, and general guidelines for reviewing, referencing, and handing ineffective essays. In the following chapter, EUCLID (2019, 5-13) examines the plague of plagiarism and provided tips with typical examples of plagiarism that can be avoided; mainly through citations, paraphrasing, and the proper use of quotations. The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) Crib Sheet covered in Chapter eight is one of a family of style guides that have outlined the standard procedures for page formatting; citations (End/Footnotes) and the proper use of capitalizations, abbreviations, compounds words, and numbers in academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 44).

The basic similarities and differences between American English and British English were expounded with useful illustrations in chapter six (EUCLID 2019, 27-35). Characteristic differences in spellings, grammar, vocabulary, and general usage were clearly outlined. This is preceded by an introductory note explaining the reasons for the observed differences.

Finally, the last chapter and topic to be discussed here explore the meaning and usage of various Latin abbreviations and expressions. I will be discussing the five selected chapters highlighted above in the following pages. The ACA-401D period on the coursepack also included a thirteen-minutes video that guides EUCLID students on how to use Zotero to manage citations and bibliographies.

2) REACTION

a) The Basics of Essay Writing

The first chapter of the first study period of ACA-401D coursepack titled ‘The Basics of Essay Writing’ provided a concise account of six essential steps to writing evidence-based academic essays (EUCLID 2019, 1-4). This basic guide presented in the first chapter of this coursepack is fundamental to the understanding of international academic writing, a writing style that is markedly different from the everyday formal and informal workplace writing. In contrast to the real world, where we experience our lives, Levin (2006, 5) asserts that ‘The academic world, on the other hand, is one of the theories, explanations, ideas, and critiques...the culture of higher education in the western world is very much a culture of the written word’. It is therefore expedient that there is a definitive guide and consensus as to what the basic steps to essay writing should be.

At the time of writing this paper, a google search on this subject revealed varying information on the number of steps to basic essay writing. However, what is consistent is that these articles are all indicative of a road map that consists of the following processes: starting the essay, drawing on the work of other writers and researchers by researching the topic, organizing your ideas, and writing the essay beginning with a draft that structures an essay in a way that communicates the writer’s ideas. This is followed by referencing the essay, which is an important way to guard against plagiarism, and finally, editing and handing in the final essay (EUCLID 2019, 4).

But transiting from the typical day-to-day work- or business-related writing to the higher standard required for international academic writing can be a daunting task for especially new doctoral students. This is further complicated according to Lamberg (1977, 26) by ‘...the inappropriate emphasis on the finished product and the corresponding neglect of the process of composing. One manifestation of that neglect has been the failure to consider errors and weaknesses in the finished papers as symptomatic of more serious difficulties students may be having while engaged in the process of preparing and writing papers and while dealing with the practicalities of doing academic assignments generally’. I have also found from personal experience that there are indeed several essay writing

hurdles to be surmounted before getting to this final product. It is important that new doctoral students are forewarned about these hurdles and provided with practical advice on how they can avoid and or deal with them. The notable ones I have had to deal with include procrastination, distraction due to family demands, and the dreaded writer's block that may be compounded by the typical online student's work schedule. To jumpstart this writing endeavour, I have had to request *a leave of absence* so that I can focus exclusively on the task at hand, and develop the habits needed to complete other writing assignments.

Moreover, the fact that every course taken at EUCLID will comprise writing five standard response papers, one quiz, and a major paper is a testament to EUCLID's commitment to helping students build excellent skills in international writing through constant practice. To fulfil my dream of being a writer, I had in January this year, procured about forty books from Amazon including the 99th annual edition of *Writer's Market (2020)* regarded as 'the most trusted guide to getting published' according to its publishers, the *Writer's Digest Books*. This is in addition to a previous collection of sixty-two mostly large volume books ranging from biographies such as 'State at Any Cost' by Tom Segev to several others in the field of politics, social science, history, development, and psychology. However, after reading several of these books, the task of writing this first response paper was an arduous one I must confess. It became clear to me that *it is one thing to be an avid reader and another, to be a writer*. Although reading may improve and complement your writing ability, it does not replace the prerequisite need for a full understanding of the fundamentals of the writing process, its various techniques, and repeated practice. There is indeed a big difference between getting well acquainted with the finished product of a writer and being able to write a good one yourself.

The contents of EUCLID's ACA401D coursepack (period one) is arguably a major part of the missing link. I consider the content of this course to be highly valuable. It will also be helpful if readers acquaint themselves with additional reference materials including two to three additional examples of good response papers. To highlight the importance of students, access to examples, Alford and Griffin (2019) claims that student's exposure to an increased number of examples is a powerful way to broaden and deepen students learning. There is no doubt that devoting time and effort to the practice of mind mapping, organization of ideas, and essay planning for a good number of essay topics will *fast-track* students' understanding and ultimately lead to the mastery of the basic steps explained in chapter one. Since writing an essay will in most cases involve varying degrees of literature reviews, EUCLID admonishes students to guard against presenting other people's ideas as though they were theirs, an act referred to as plagiarism. The next paragraph will examine plagiarism and how to avoid them.

b) Plagiarism

When Kate Turabian, the University of Chicago's dissertation secretary published a guideline for student writers in 1937, the current world of electronic technologies was not envisioned. Nevertheless, the vast plethora of internet resources and word processing software have not altered the student writer's rudimentary task of executing research endeavours that are compliant with the accepted standard for citation, style, and formatting

(Kate 2007, 10). In an article published in the journal *Issues in Educational Research*, Teh and Paull (2013, 295) assert that despite the vast literature on plagiarism, research into the continued divergence of perception and attitudes of both students and faculty is nonetheless deficient.

EUCLID (2019, 5-13) provided examples of plagiarism and other terms related to situations where the 'normal academic ethics of hard work, individual effort and recognition of the work of others have failed leading to a "cheating culture"' in the words of Crittenden, Hanna, and Peterson (2009). According to EUCLID (2019, 5), plagiarism is simply defined as a situation where 'the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information'.

What is more disturbing is the likelihood that, a writer's yearning to impress his readers may lead him or her to unintentionally present other people's ideas as his own especially when limited literature review on a subject has been conducted or through an inability to adequately cite other men's work. Perhaps academicians may wish to consider classifying plagiarism into three levels (e.g., level I, II & III) to define its severity. A famous Mark Twain's quote read thus: 'There is no such thing as a new idea. It is impossible. We simply take a lot of old ideas and put them into a sort of mental kaleidoscope...but they are the same old pieces of coloured glass that have been in use through all ages. (Goodreads 2020). I couldn't agree more with these words extracted from Mark Twain's autobiography. The internet is packed with sensational stories of famous journalists, academics, and professionals '*caught in the act*' of plagiarism (Green 1981; Bailey 2012; and Bailey 2017). The extensive media coverage given to these scandals has boosted the campaign for originality and compliance to the 'normal academic ethics of hard work, individual effort and recognition of the work of others...' cited by Crittenden, Hanna, and Peterson (2009).

Thankfully, EUCLID (2019, 9-10) has described instances when a writer is not obligated to cite. This is particularly true for all information considered to be 'common knowledge' material found in numerous texts or publications. This is also the case for persons reviewing new subject areas they are not accustomed to. EUCLID (2019, 10), therefore recommends that students classify details as 'common knowledge' when they are traced to 'many different sources'. I consider this material to be helpful. There is, however, a need to revise this material in a manner that merges chapter two with chapter eight since plagiarism is well within the concepts addressed in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) Crib sheet contained in chapter eight of this coursepack.

c) Chicago Manual of Style

This section is an exposition into the Chicago Style of formatting also referred to as the 'Turabian style' by Dr Abel Scribe who defined the Chicago Style as the style of formatting books and research papers documented in two identical but distinct publications of the University of Chicago Press: the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 1996 (EUCLID 2019, 44). The simplicity of the Turabian style to the student context explains why it is the

style of choice for students. I find Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers to be an indispensable learning resource. One of the distinguishing features of the Turabian style is that it provides an invaluable guide into the writing process briefly highlighted in the following paragraph.

Secondly, the CMS Crib Sheet presented by Dr Abel Scribe in the eighth chapter of ACA-401D coursepack is divided into three sections: the first examines CMS rule on the appropriate use and application of abbreviations, acronyms, capitalizations, and compound words. Others include quotations, dates and numbers, and effects used in making emphases such as italics and quotes. The second section is a rule guide for page formatting. The third and last section explains how notes (footnote and endnotes) and bibliographies are used (EUCLID 2019, 44-55). There is no doubt that mastery of the Chicago Manual of Style requires repeated reading so mastery can be acquired at the earliest. It is worthy to appreciate how one scholar's resolve to write a manual of style has indeed transformed international academic writing.

Turabian (2007, 16) urges writers to note that every report done well, will add to the writer's ability to do the next report better, and most certainly, the better one can judge other people's writings. But then, the accurate assessment of a research report is more likely to be dependent on a critical appraisal that is based on evidence and reasoning we can rely on. Turabian (2007, 16) further asserts that while the alternative to the critical approach may be to rely on tradition and authority or intuition, spiritual insights among other unverifiable concepts, we are most likely to fail to convince others as to why they too should believe as we have come to believe. Suffice it to say that 'We must do more than just state an opinion and describe our feelings'. (Turabian 2007, 16). The eighth chapter of ACA-401D coursepack is therefore devoted to helping students construct research reports that are predicated on the verifiable fact that readers can reasonably 'accept as truths independent of the writer's feelings and beliefs', (Turabian 2007, 16).

In a nutshell, the Chicago Manual of Style reviewed in the eighth chapter of this coursepack has described in an easy-to-understand format, how the presence of both specific and general source materials can easily be done in a way that makes distinctions between sources without complicating citations (Macmillan and Kotch 2011, 3-11). According to David Macmillan and Robert Kotch, simply giving evidence is never enough, you always need to explain how the source can be used to support your claim and the overall purpose of your paper.

d) American Vs. British English

American and British English are two varieties of world English understood to be more similar than they are different with most differences attributed to both countries' varying cultural and historical developments, and how these two variants have evolved (EUCLID 2019, 27). Several factors have reportedly led to the steady growth and current global dominance of American English over British English. There is no gainsaying the fact that factors such as staggering population advantage, her position as the greatest economy in the world, and the influence of American mass media technology, compared

with that of the British accounts for the current dominant influence of American English on ‘world English’ (EUCLID 2019, 27).

The sixth chapter of ACA-401D coursepack (period one) has examined similarities and differences in spellings, pronunciation, meanings grammar, and general usage. George Bernard Shaw, the famous poet, and writer is reputed to have stated in a satirical tone that ‘England and America are two countries separated by the same language’. (Goodreads 2020). The following paragraph will justify such characterization. The interplay between similarities and differences is succinctly explained as follows: same pronunciation but different spelling (e.g., cheque vs check); same spellings but different pronunciation; same words but different meanings; and same concept but different expressions (petrol vs gasoline). EUCLID (2019, 27-35).

I would add that the Microsoft Word processing software has been the major tool that has put the need for consistency in the use of a particular type of English language. The software is programmed to underline using a red line, typewritten words that are not consistent with the selected version of the English language. Until recently, I had considered the formatting done by Microsoft Word to be sufficient. But after reading this coursepack, it is clear, that a lot more is expected of countries where English is not the native language. At EUCLID, the American variant is preferable, but students are required to select and maintain consistency in the usage of any of the two variants. I have resorted to adopting British English at this time for the simple reason that I have used this version more than any other giving my country’s history as a British colony.

e) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

The last chapter of the ACA-401D coursepack (period one) examines the meanings and usage of Latin abbreviations and expressions commonly used in writings (EUCLID 2019, 56). I consider this topic to be very useful considering the relatively extensive use of Latin abbreviations and expressions in pharmaceutical and medical terminology. Before joining public health practice, I had worked as a pharmacist at several medical and pharmaceutical centres where Latin expressions are an integral part of everyday drug prescription services. But since joining the public health field, I have only come across a very limited number of Latin expressions.

EUCLID (2019, 56) notes for emphasis that ‘it is best to create content using ‘plain language’ principles that are simple and direct, but not simplistic or patronizing’. This chapter also discourages the use of abbreviations, acronyms, and jargon. It further recommends that the English equivalent of Latin abbreviations are used in business, formal, and technical writing to avoid misinterpretation by readers. while stating that the English equivalent of abbreviation is used in business, formal, and technical writing to avoid misinterpretation by readers.

According to the writing centre at University of North Carolina (UNC) college of Art and Science, the APA, MLA, and Chicago style manual all recommend that writers should keep Latin abbreviation out of the main body of a text with exceptions (such as e.g.,

etc. and i.e.) which must be placed in parenthesis. From the foregoing, it is not surprising for anyone to wonder why writers have to learn Latin abbreviations and expressions if they are less likely to use them in academic writing. Despite the preference of English phrases over Latin abbreviations in academic writing, UNC (2019) asserts that Latin abbreviations and expressions have survived till this day because ‘they contain a lot of meaning in very small packages. Consequently, writers who decide not to use Latin abbreviations are most likely going to encounter them in other writers’ texts’. This, therefore, justifies the time we have put into the last four paragraphs, and even more, the plethora of literature on Latin abbreviations and expression available in print and online.

3) **CONCLUSION**

EUCLID’s ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack (period one) revised by Prof Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr Kabir Gulma, examined within eight insightful chapters, the techniques required for creating concise, informative, and compelling essays that conform with international academic writing standards. My learning experiences have been truly rewarding. I am particularly enthusiastic about achieving my innate goal of being an author and publisher. I am also optimistic that completing the entire seven periods in ACA-401D coursepack will help me achieve my goals. I will not hesitate to recommend EUCLID’s program to colleagues at work.

REFERENCES

- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period I*. Bangui, Central African Republic: EUCLID University.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2020. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.
- Crittenden, Victoria, Richard C. Hanna, and Robert A. Peterson. 2009: ‘The Cheating Culture: A Global Societal Phenomenon’. *Business Horizons* 52, no. 4 (July 1, 2009): 337–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.02.004>.
- Lamberg, Walter. 1977. ‘Major Problems in Doing Academic Writing’. *College Composition and Communication* 28, no. 1 (1977): 26–29. <https://doi.org/10.2307/356889>.
- Levin, Peter. 2006. *Write Great Essays! A Guide to Reading and Essay Writing for Undergraduates and Taught Postgraduates*. Reprinted. Student-Friendly Guides. Maidenhead: Open Univ. Press.
- Teh E., and M. Paull. 2013. ‘Reducing the Prevalence of Plagiarism: A Model for Staff, Students, and Universities’. *Issues in Educational Research* 23, no. 2 (June 14, 2013): 283–98. <http://www.iier.org.au/iier23/teh.html>.

Turabian, Kate L. 2007. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C Booth, Gregory G Colomb, Joseph M Williams, and Wayne Chicago. University of Chicago Press.

Alford, Ken, and Griffin, Tyler 2019. 'Unleashing the Power of Examples'. Accessed December 18, 2020. <https://www.facultyfocus.com/articles/effective-teaching-strategies/unleashing-the-power-of-examples/>.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.